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Global Landslide Susceptibility Mapping Using Multi-Model Machine Learning Approaches on Geospatial Satellite Data

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Abstract—Landslides globally represent a big threat to society and people, making accurate susceptibility models increasingly necessary in risk mitigation. We present a high-resolution, global-scale landslide susceptibility model that integrates several machine learning (ML) methodologies into a multi-model framework. Our approach aims to improve on the one used by NASA in 2016, to create a more reliable model through the use of a new rich global landslide catalog for training (UGLC), more accurate through the use of a global DEM at 90m (MERIT DEM) along with over 100 global predictive variables tracing the topographic, geological and environmental asset. Model development is done on high performance computing (HPC) for the required operational performance and to ensure model scalability with the injection of new data. In order to create a reliable and interpretable model that can support future dynamic early warning systems, linking baseline susceptibility mapping with phenomenon monitoring, enabling real-time disaster response, marking a milestone in global landslide risk assessment.

I. INTRODUCTION

Landslides represent a significant natural hazard with global implications, impacting human settlements and infrastructure. Traditional landslide susceptibility mapping (LSM) efforts have been constrained by data integration challenges and computational limitations [15]. Understanding landslide susceptibility is critical

for effective hazard mitigation and risk assessment, especially in densely populated areas [8]. Recent advancements in HPC and the availability of global data enable the development of large-scale models that improve predictive capabilities and generalizability [17]. This study introduces a global scale 90m resolution landslide susceptibility model leveraging a multi-model approach, incorporating machine learning (ML) techniques to enhance landslide susceptibility predictions by using high-resolution satellite data and robust computational methods [3, 8]. Traditionally, LSMs have been constrained to highly detailed sub-continental scale models due to the computational demands and complexities associated with large-scale data integration and model generalization [9, 15]. However, advances in high-performance computing (HPC) and the expanded availability of global satellite data now enable the development of LSM at a global level [17]. By leveraging HPC, we address the diverse global complexities of landslides, including variability in topography, geology, climate, and triggering mechanisms [16, 17]. The model harmonizes datasets across multiple spatial resolutions, ensuring a scalable, interpretable, and flexible solution for worldwide landslide monitoring [14, 21].

II. METHOD

The project builds upon NASA’s 2016 landslide susceptibility model [17], incorporating substantial enhancements. Notable model advancements include a richer training dataset based on the Unified Global Landslide Catalog (UGLC). UGLC is a new global landslide catalogue created in the framework of this project, which combines 27 global datasets standardized at various scales, contributing over one million points and polygons (fig. 1) [10, 11].

Figure 1. Unified Global Landslide Catalog (UGLC) point data distribution across the globe.

This catalogue provides more carefully categorized landslide records along with non-landslide data derived from a pixel-wise thresholding combined with dynamic buffers to minimize spatial autocorrelation and reduce overfitting risks [15, 21]. This is complemented by the MERIT DEM, a 90-meter resolution elevation [20] model that replaces NASA’s 1 km SRTM DEM, enhancing spatial accuracy [17]. Additionally, the predictor features have been expanded from 4 to over 100, spanning terrain morphology, hydrology, soil characteristics, seismic activity, and geological indicators [1, 2, 5, 6, 7, 13, 19, 20]. This approach provides a more robust framework for susceptibility mapping and supports the integration of real-time trigger data [8, 14, 16]. Methodologically, this project employs a multi-model strategy that combines ensemble-based ML techniques (Random Forest) [4, 9, 18] and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) for spatial pattern recognition [3,21]. Ensemble learning methods capitalize on the strengths of each individual model to ensure model interpretability and transferability across regions, allowing a dynamic adjustment to region-specific conditions, especially improving generalization in regions with limited landslide data [21]. To validate the robustness of the model across diverse geographical settings, k-fold and block cross-validation is employed. This validation considers subsets of training points grouped by trigger type, landslide type, and date range, ensuring relevance across temporal and spatial domains [15]. Due to the computational demands of the massive processing of satellite datasets and executing ML algorithms, the use of HPC resources is necessitated [16]. Our framework utilizes parallel processing across HPC nodes and distributed learning on GPU clusters, enabling efficient handling

of high-dimensional data and accelerating model training [8]. This setup facilitates spatially detailed analysis and shortens computational time, making it feasible to deploy a large-scale global LSM model [17].

III. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

In this preliminary testing phase, we evaluated the main 49 out of over 100 proposed predictors, focusing on highly informative global raster from sources like MERIT DEM90m [19], SOILGRIDv1. [7], Geomorpho90m [2] and Hydrography90m (1) using a subsample of 50K train/test points (25K presence randomly picked from the UGLC, and 25K absence randomly picked using a morpho-topographic thresholding retaining only locations with a minimum slope of 5°). Although this approach will be refined in our final model, it has been shown in the literature [12] to be both straightforward and highly effective at identifying non-landslide areas.

A. MLP test on a 50K subsampled Dataset

A limited preliminary test was carried out on a simple 2 hidden layer MLP architecture using a subsample of only 25000 presence and 25000 absence points (Tab.1).

TABLE I. MULTI-LAYER PERCEPTRON TEST

Setting					
Hidden Layers/Nodes	Epochs	Learning Rate	Optimizer	Criterion	Test size
1 ^o /16 (ReLU) 2 ^o /32 (ReLU)	100	0.01	ADAM	Cross Entropy Loss	0.2

The model achieved a rapid convergence (fig.2) and high performances but highlighting some overfitting issues (Tab.2).

Figure 2. Performance diagram of MLP test on 25k UGLC landslide points.

TABLE II. MULTI-LAYER PERCEPTRON PERFORMANCES

Evaluation index		Value	
Precision		93.16	
Recall		94.57	
F1 score		93.86	
Confusion Matrix			
True Label	0	10899	915
	1	716	12470
		0	1
		Predicted Label	

B. RF test on a 50K subsampled Dataset

Subsequent model tests were carried out on HPC with the same subsample of 25000 presence and 25000 absence points on a Random Forest (RF) architecture (Tab.3).

TABLE III. RANDOM FOREST TEST

Setting		
Number of estimators	Observation samples	Test size
300	5	0.2

This model showed a high performance, with even greater accuracy scores (Tab.4). Also in this test, as with the MLP, high levels of performance seem coupled with high misclassification rates, highlighting some shared issues likely related to the training sample (Tab.4).

TABLE IV. RANDOM FOREST PERFORMANCES

Evaluation index		Value	
Precision		0.9565	
Recall		0.9670	
F1 score		0.9628	
Confusion Matrix			
True Label	0	23900	1100
	1	825	24175
		0	1
		Predicted Label	

C. Joint Model Features Analysis

A more in-depth comparative analysis of the two tested models was carried out by employing a SHAP analysis on the MLP to capture local and directional effects in a non-linear model (Fig.3) and a Permutation Feature Importance Analysis (PFIA) on the RF model (Fig.4). Both MLP-SHAP and RF-PFIA consistently rank topographic and soil predictors (e.g. rough-magnitude_90M, ELEV, CLYPPT) as most influential, reflecting robust underlying patterns. RF-PFIA concentrates on terrain-derived metrics used in high-level splits, whereas SHAP yields a more diffuse attribution profile that captures non-linear interactions. SHAP uniquely provides directional impact and per-observation variability of feature effects. Thus, MLP-SHAP and RF-PFIA are coherent in ranking but quantitatively slightly diverge due to model architecture and ranking methodology.

Figure 3. SHAP Analysis on MLP test with 25K presence and 25K absence points.

Figure 4. Feature Importance Analysis on RF test with all 1M presence and 1M absence points.

IV. FUTURE IMPROVEMENTS

Preliminary tests revealed consequences related to spatial and temporal inhomogeneity in the distribution of points in the dataset, thus leading to the need to develop a data balancing system. This system to be introduced in the forthcoming tests will be based on point density and thematic subdivision of the tests by climate, event date and landslide type (thanks to the standardized information available in UGLC records), in order to improve model generalizability and error mapping. Moreover, different methods of morpho-topographic thresholding or buffering for a more precise sampling of non-landslide points [12] will also be tested, in order to pick non-landslide points as reliable as those present in the UGLC. Finally, in addition to the already planned validation with the polygons of the UGLC, we want to introduce a spatial-temporal cross-validation methodologies for thematic blocks (geographic, time, typology and climatic areas), and a final comparison phase with traditional detailed landslide susceptibility maps, obtained at a smaller scale. All this is highly necessary in order to model such a complex phenomenon, with heterogeneous and not always complete data, on a global scale [9].

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this scalable global landslide susceptibility model, exploiting ML with a multi-model approach due to computation on HPC, opens new horizons on global-scale modeling of landslide susceptibility; highlighting how multi-model methods not only improve prediction accuracy, but also offer enhanced interpretability, which is essential for informed decision making. Thus, providing a concrete basis for future global early warning systems through dynamic integration of up-to-date or real-time data, moving from susceptibility mapping to an operational early warning tool that aids global disaster preparedness and response.

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